

Studies on some Binary and Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II)

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Potentiometric studies on binary and ternary complexes of Ni^{II} ion with 1,3-dihydroxy-4-(2'-pyridylazo)benzene (PAR, H₂L), 1-(2'-arsonophenylazo)-2-hydroxynaphthalene-3,6-disulphonic acid (APANS, H₂L), pyrogallol sulphophthalein (PGR, H₂L), and with pairs of ligands; PAR-ethylenediamine (en, A), APANS-en, PGR-en, PAR-1,10 phenanthroline (pn, A), APANS-pn, PGR-pn, have been carried out at 20° ($\mu=0.10$ M KNO₃). The experimental data analysed over a pH range 2.6–11.0 show the formation of NiHL⁺, NiL, NiL(OH)⁻, Ni(HL)₂, NiHL₂⁻, NiL₂²⁻, NiHLA⁺ (with PAR, en and pn); NiLA(OH)⁻ (with PAR and en); NiH₂L⁻, NiHL⁺, NiL²⁻, NiH₂LA⁻, NiHLA⁺, NiLA²⁻ (with APANS, en and pn); NiH₂L, NiHL⁻, NiL²⁻, Ni₂L, Ni₂L(OH)⁻, NiH₂LA, NiHLA⁻, NiLA²⁻ (with PGR and pn). The corresponding equilibrium constants [except the PAR complexes, NiHL⁺, Ni(HL)₂, NiHL₂⁻, NiHLA⁺ (with en and pn), where precipitation of the reaction mixture did not allow calculation] have been evaluated and the results discussed.

IN an earlier work on Cu^{II} complexes with the ligands PAR, APANS, PGR, and pair of ligands PAR-en, APANS-en, PGR-en, PAR-pn, APANS-pn, PGR-pn, we reported interesting information¹ especially with PGR systems; where protonated (CuH₂L), mixed protonated-hydroxo (CuH₂L(OH)⁻) and protonated mixed ligand (CuH₂LA) complexes are formed at low pH involving the coordination position, ketonic oxygen and the adjacent phenolic oxygen. The coordination position is changed in the species CuHL(OH)²⁻, CuL(OH)²⁻, CuHLA(OH)²⁻ and CuLA(OH)²⁻. This continuing potentiometric study on the complexation reaction of these ligands has been carried out with Ni^{II} ion at 20° ($\mu=0.10$ M KNO₃). Stability constants of the existing equilibria have been evaluated using previously described procedure and the method of calculation¹⁻⁶; and the metal-ligand interactions have been discussed.

Experimental

CO₂-free 0.1929 N NaOH, 0.02284 N HNO₃ and 1.0 M KNO₃ solutions were prepared using G.R. grade chemicals.

A 1.0 × 10⁻³ M Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (AnalaR) solution was prepared and metal content was determined by EDTA titration method⁷. 5.0 × 10⁻³ M solutions of each ligand, PAR, APANS (disodium salt), PGR, pn (all Loba, G.R.) and en (AnalaR) were prepared by direct weighing (5.0 cm³ of 0.1929 N NaOH was added in 250 cm³ measuring flask to dissolve PGR).

The following mixtures, (i) 2.284 × 10⁻³ N HNO₃; (ii) 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M ligand + (i); (iii) 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + (ii); (iv) 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + (ii); (v) 1.0 × 10⁻³ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + (ii) (only in PGR system); (vi) 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M PAR/APANS/PGR + 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M A; (vii) 1.0 × 10⁻³ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M PGR + 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M A;

(viii) 1.0 × 10⁻³ M Ni(NO₃)₂ + 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M PGR + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M A; were prepared and titrated potentiometrically and pH vs *a* (moles of alkali used per mole of ligand) curves were obtained as described earlier^{1,3,5}.

Results and Discussion

Binary system: At initial pH (below *a*=1.60), the 1:1, Ni^{II}-PAR mixture turned turbid, which did not permit calculation on the existing equilibrium below *a*=1. However, a steep inflection at *a*=1 (pH ~5.0, Fig. 1) indicates the formation of NiHL⁺ species involving azo group, one phenolic oxygen and basic nitrogen (1). A clear red solution obtained at pH ~8.25 (*a*=1.60) does not change upto *a*=3.0. Increase in *a* values beyond *a*=1 may be due to either deprotonation and subsequent hydrolysis of the deprotonated species or hydrolysis of the protonated species followed by deprotonation of the mixed protonated hydroxo species or further hydrolysis. But, these steps can not be analysed by the earlier described methods^{1,2,5} due to turbidity formation at low pH. Considering equilibrium NiHL⁺ ⇌ NiL + H⁺ (between *a*=1 and 2), the calculated log *K* value is given in Table 1.

The 1:2, Ni^{II}-PAR mixture, which is also turbid red, turns into a clear solution at *a*=1.55. A steep inflection in pH vs *a* curve at *a*=1 (pH ~5.5, Fig. 1) shows simultaneous formation of NiHL⁺ and Ni(HL)₂ species. The mode of dissociation of proton or association of OH⁻ beyond *a*=1 cannot be recognised due to precipitation by the known methods. The equilibrium NiHL₂⁻ ⇌ NiL₂²⁻ + H⁺ (between *a*=1.5 and 2) can reasonably be accepted on account of no increase in *a* value beyond 2, where perhaps due to coordination saturation (the ligand units acting as a tridentate ligand

inspite of the high pK value of one of the two OH groups, bound to As (2), its larger distance from the coordinated Ni^{II} ion, high OH⁻ ion concentration, liberation of H⁺ ion from NiHL²⁻ species (between $a=2$ and 3), indicates a structural change (*i.e.* coordination through phenolic oxygen, azo group, one hydroxy oxygen bound to As, similar to Cu^{II}-APANS¹ and Th^{IV}-APANS⁹ complexes) in the formation of NiHL²⁻ (3) between $a=1$ and 2, where shifting of electron density from OH group to coordinated Ni^{II} ion, through As would be favoured leading to dissociation of proton from NiHL²⁻ species. Further, the titration curves (Fig. omitted) show the absence of 1 : 2 complex.

PGR solution is turbid below $a=0.6$ (pH ~ 3.0) due to little solubility of the neutral H₂L species. On addition of an equal amount of Ni^{II} ion the turbidity is unaffected, but a gradual colour change, light red to dark red, dark red to violet appears, respectively, at pH $\sim 3.0-6.6$ (upto $a=1.95$) and above 6.60. A weak inflection at $a=2$ (Fig. omitted) indicates formation of NiH₂L dark red species. The favourable coordinating groups are expected to be ketonic and adjacent phenolic oxygen (4). Beyond $a=2$, proton dissociation from NiH₂L was confirmed by the previously described method^{1,2,5}. However, a new structural arrangement (5, between $a=2$ and 3) can clearly explain the liberation of protons upto $a=4$. The suggested structure is supported by an ir study on rare earth-PGR complexes in solution¹⁰.

The pH vs a curves (Fig. omitted) show that not more than one ligand molecules are attached with the metal ion while there is simultaneous attachment of two Ni^{II} ion with one ligand molecule below $a=4$ (pH ~ 7.5). Beyond $a=4$, the expected reaction is Ni₂L + OH⁻ \rightleftharpoons Ni₂L(OH)⁻, and the colour of Ni₂L(OH)⁻ appears dark violet. Evaluated equilibrium constants are given in Table 1.

Ternary system : The 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-PAR-pn mixture is also turbid upto pH ~ 8.25 ($a=1.35$) and colour remains red throughout the titration. Comparison of titration curves (Fig. 1) indicates that pn is first attached with Ni^{II} ion and subsequently PAR is associated in second step. NiAHL⁺ is independently formed between $a=0$ and 1 (pH ~ 2.8 and 7.0) but the presence of turbidity did not permit calculations of equilibrium constants. Above $a=1.35$, calculated log K for NiAHL⁺ \rightleftharpoons NiAL + H⁺, has been reported in Table 1. The 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-PAR-en mixture also remains turbid between pH ~ 2.8

and 8.3 ($a=1.61$) due to the formation of insoluble NiHL⁺ and NiHLA⁺ species. The binary complex formed at pH ~ 4.50 reacts with en between pH ~ 4.50 and 7.10 (Fig. 1). Further, assuming the equilibria, NiHLA⁺ \rightleftharpoons NiLA + H⁺, NiLA + OH⁻ \rightleftharpoons NiLA(OH)⁻, respectively between $a=1$ and 2, $a=2$ and 3, the corresponding equilibrium constants were calculated (Table 1).

The light orange colour of 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-APANS-pn mixture gradually changes to red from pH ~ 4.75 . Existence of equilibrium, NiA²⁺ + H₂L²⁻ \rightleftharpoons NiAH₂L⁻ is evident from the titration curves (Fig. omitted). Further, stepwise deprotonation of the uncoordinated groups in this species has been proved to involve structural changes as observed in binary system. The 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-APANS-en mixture is also initially light orange which gradually changes to red from pH ~ 4.69 . Stepwise association of H₂L²⁻ (primary ligand) and A (secondary ligand) with Ni^{II} ion in the formation of NiH₂LA⁻ is indicated by the titration curves (Fig. omitted), and also existence of the species NiHLA²⁻ and NiLA²⁻ has been confirmed between $a=1$ and 2 and 3, respectively. The corresponding equilibrium constants are given in Table 1.

Absence of turbidity, only one change in colour, (*i.e.* light red to dark red from pH ~ 5.7) unlike binary system in the 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-PGR-pn mixture and nature of titration curves (Fig. omitted) show the formation of NiAH₂L, NiAHL⁻, NiAL²⁻ between $a=0$ and 2, 2 and 3, 3 and 4, respectively. There is no indication of the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-PGR-en ; 2 : 1 : 1, 2 : 1 : 2, Ni^{II}-PGR-pn and Ni^{II}-PGR-en complexes.

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